

DIACHRONIC ANALYSIS OF SOCIO-POLITICAL VOCABULARY

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ABSTRACT

The question of the historical dynamics of socio-political vocabulary in journalism is of particular importance for the diachronic analysis of socio-political vocabulary in a journalistic text. It is known that language, as the most important element of speech, is communication, communication, and influence, and at the same time, due to its extremely expanding capabilities, it performs the noble social task of transferring experience and knowledge accumulated by man. society for future generations. In the process of formation and development of a language, it goes through a life path. As a result of the socio-political changes that have taken place in connection with gaining independence, many new words, expressions, and combinations have naturally appeared in our language. This situation is observed mainly in the fields of science, production, economics, international relations, and law, and partly in the fields of education, culture, art, and fiction. Of course, when introducing these concepts and applying them, it was necessary to justify why the options recommended as norms were approved in this way.

Introduction. As the vocabulary of the language is constantly changing and enriching, the processes of updating functional styles are regular. Journalism is a method that develops rapidly with society, and the fact that it is oriented towards sociality reflects the life of the state and society in journalistic texts. The public is informed about political and social news through media text. The predominance of extra-linguistic factors in the development of language shows the influence of a person, and the society he belongs to, on the language, and naturally, none of the external factors exist outside of the person, and the society he belongs to. The well-known linguists H. Nematov and R. Rasulov gave the following opinion about the development of language and the stages of the speech process: "Language exists in the minds of the members of society, it is ready, common, mandatory for all of them, the units that serve

to form and express thought and their interactions it is considered as a sum of perceptions about their relations"¹.

Regarding the diachronic analysis of the language, the linguist scientist E.V. We found it necessary to refer to Burdaev's assumptions in this regard. Here, it is important to take into account the scientist's thesis about the need to distinguish between specific (exactly) diachronic and retrospective analysis aimed at the study of events characteristic of a certain historical period. inverted) synchronicity'. Because the synchronous and retrospective approaches are based only on the study of non-temporal (non-temporary) laws, firstly - in the present time, and secondly, by approaching history. Unlike them, "diachronic analysis, by its essence, is primarily aimed at determining temporal (temporary) changes or the absence of these changes in the studied phenomena." Undoubtedly, the diachronic approach based on the comparison of data from different periods in the analysis of the material "has a great heuristic potential, because it allows observing the evolution of the national worldview and linguistic tools, embodies it, establishes the characteristics of each stage, shows the characteristics of the interaction of language, politics, and culture. makes it possible". Indeed, "... socio-political lexicon has a long history of development. The earliest words related to statehood are found in the ancient book "Avesta".

With its historical formation, this social institution of society has developed over centuries. This process, of course, is reflected in the language, especially in its historical lexicon. Therefore, it is natural for the socio-political lexicon to emerge from words related to different languages. The study of the diachronic development of the socio-political lexicon, which initially consisted of a group of isolated observations with significantly different goals and methods, at this stage is gradually becoming one of the rapidly developing directions of the science located at the intersection of linguistics and political science. After all, "...our language has delivered to us generations as an immortal heritage the unique experience and valuable values of our wise ancestors, our priceless spiritual and educational wealth, it has unquestioningly performed the function of an indestructible bridge connecting several generations between times".

It is well known that Amir Temur ruled his country with the opinion that in politics advice, consideration, and thinking are ten times more useful than the force of arms. This idea means solving the conflicting issues in the current era through political dialogue and diplomacy. To generalize, diplomacy is a component of foreign policy, a means of the peace that realizes its international activities with the use of basic methods-negotiations. Modern diplomacy is a non-military practical event, a set of methods. Diplomacy is the art of peaceful negotiations to prevent international conflicts and deepen international cooperation. Amir Temur's political and diplomatic dialogues with the rulers of countries other than Movarunnahr show that all the issues of his international policy are mainly aimed at solving them based on the Islamic perspective. "I learned from experience," he said, "if the state is not built based on religion, then the power and order of the kingdom will be lost." Amir Temur has always paid great attention to keeping Islam as an ideological flag in his political relations

¹ Будаев Э.В., Кондратьева О.Н. и др. Методика диахронического анализ политических метафорыки. Политическая лингвистика 6 (60). ' 2016. – С.18-34.

with other countries and peoples, always keeping it at the center of attention as the main issue. During the reign of Amir Temur, a special corps of diplomats was created.

Well-educated, well-educated people who can speak several languages are attracted here. Timur always observed that everyone followed the principle of "not killing the ambassador", which was recognized by the people and rooted in ancient times. Amir Temur's brilliant political activity was continued by his descendants even after his death. Ambassadors from the court of the Timurid princes to foreign countries, reception ceremonies of foreign ambassadors in the court of the Timurids, and correspondence with foreign rulers, in short, there is a lot of information about the foreign relations of the Timurids that can be found in the historical works. possible In the palace of the Timurids, every issue, such as organizing an embassy in a foreign country, welcoming ambassadors from abroad, organizing reception ceremonies, and providing services to ambassadors, was appointed. The munshi devan operated in the palace and it was the responsibility of the maker devan to ensure that the letters sent to foreign kings and sultans on behalf of the Timurid ruler were decorated with perfect, feminine phrases, and on the contrary, to translate and copy letters from foreign rulers.

In general, since the diplomatic relations of Amir Temur and Timurid princes with foreign rulers covered wide geographical areas and long periods, it is not possible to cover them in detail. Some of the above-mentioned pieces of evidence prove that the Timurid diplomacy was based on the traditions of the great state founded by Amir Temur and that some aspects of these policies have been inherited by us. When we look at the documents and correspondence kept in the office of that time, we come across such lexicons related to socio-political concepts²: farman, label, noma, yoso (yosok, yosog), molu jihat, munshi (mirza), peshkash, raiyat, suyurghol, sovrnun, sari sumor, tiyul, fatwa, tuzuk (tuzukot, tura, and tuzuk), ulufa, khiroj, kholisa, khana, sumor, shilon, large (yarku), history book, akhdos judge and others. The socio-historical analysis of these terms shows that they contain words related to the original Turkic languages (Yarliq, Yosoq, Sovrun), words borrowed from the Arabic language (devan, katib, munshi), words borrowed from the Persian-Tajik language (farman, peshkash, noma) Turkish -from the Mongolian language (yoso, nuyon) and other borrowings. At the same time, in the process of formation of working terms in all aspects of the administrative system of our republic, studying the terms used in Amir Temur's laws from the point of view of linguistics and analyzing their place in our national language can be of great practical importance.

Today, when we talk about the position of our national language in the international arena, we should, first of all, remember the past. Unfortunately, for many years, the legal rights of not only our people but also our mother tongue, the Uzbek language, were violated in the former union. Under the influence of certain artificial conditions, the position of the Uzbek language has become deplorable. When talking about the legal status of the Uzbek language in these years, it should be noted that in all the Constitutions and legal documents adopted in these years, the Uzbek language was equated with the Russian language and given equal rights. Most of the people at the top of the state and in the government offices were Russians.

² Будаев Э. В. Сопоставительная политическая метафорология моногр. – Н. Тагил : НГТСПА, 2011.– С. 142.

After that, the state language itself became only Russian. The Uzbek language is set aside as the language of departmental work. The Uzbek language was artificially used as the state language.

Its vocabulary was enriched only at the expense of the Russian language, and the national spirit was rising in the language. Below, we will generally think about the formation of the socio-political lexicon and its manifestation in journalistic style. At the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, political and social issues were regularly raised and hotly debated on the pages of the periodical press. For example, at the beginning of the 20th century, the progressive forces of society in Turkestan openly criticized some of the existing evils in the life of the country and sought ways to eliminate them. For example, in the newspaper published at that time, the following issue was written: "Some of our rich people surprised the people by having extravagant weddings and dressing each person in finery, silk, satin, and other expensive clothes. Then, before a day passes, they are surprised, after a month of the wedding, they will be broken and dishonored." In the newspapers of that time, the leader of the Turkestan Jadidist movement, the great progressive Makhmudkhoja Bekhbudi published articles, in which the problems in the cities and villages of Turkestan were highlighted.

At that time, the people were addressed to the people as a slogan in the newspapers: "Hey, parents and depositors of orphan girls, do not be honest and burn the oppressed alive." Sadoi Turkistan and Sadoi Fergana newspapers published in 1914-1915 expressed sharp opinions on political and social issues and there were efforts to wake up the nation from its centuries-long slumber. The editors of these newspapers received letters and messages from different parts of Turkestan. This period is the period of the formation of Uzbek publicists in the press. By promoting the interests of nationalism, freedom, and enlightenment, journalism became the basis for today's journalism. Writers such as Behbudi, Fitrat, Avloni, Cholpon, and Mirmuhsin Shermuhammedov tried to enlighten the public through their articles. No matter what content and idea they wrote an article about, the essence of the content of the article was to wake up the people, call for new thinking, and promote courage and self-sacrifice. Another newspaper of that time was "Taraqqi" newspaper, which covered "scientific, literary, political, scientific, commercial" topics.

The purpose of this newspaper was the idea of liberating the people from the colonial system and the development of the nation. It can be observed that rhetorical questions and exclamations are used in the text of the newspaper: "Do we Muslims have the right to freedom?" Relatives answer no a hundred times. A society dominated by lack of enlightenment and ignorance will never achieve freedom"; "tyrannical work and greedy work ... ". The socio-political life of Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century is manifested by its own development and conflicting situations. In particular, such a situation led to the gradual increase of political activity, awareness of identity, political activity, mutual solidarity, and cooperation in socio-political and cultural processes, especially after the February (1917) revolution of the Russian Empire. This led to the formation of newspaper language instead.

The Uzbek language is enriched with new concepts: "blessings of freedom"; the All-Russian Council of Muslims (National Council); "Unification of all Russian Muslims under a single political banner"; "Shuroy Islam" society, Islamic ideology; "Miftakh ul-maarif",

"Hurriyat", "Marifat va Shariat", "Ittifaqi Islamiya", "Tijarat ul-Islam", "Ravnaya ul Islam", "Gulistan", "Muayyin al-Talibin", "Jamiyati Islamiya" organizations like..." etc. Of course, the topic of the article determined the language and style of the newspaper. Here is an excerpt from the newspaper "Turkiston" founded after the revolution: "... last year Ismail Obidov, Munavvarkhan Abdurashidkhanov published the Taraqqi and Khurshid newspapers, but the government stopped their newspapers because of the anti-Khazara people. The Muslims of Turkestan are without a building, a religion, or a press as if they are speechless and deaf. I have been dreaming of serving my beloved nation impartially for a long time, but I have been thinking and thinking that there is no better way to serve. Now I know that the Muslims of Turkestan do not need anything like a newspaper written in their language." In the middle of the last century, the socio-political lexicon was activated in journalistic texts. Of course, this was due to the first increase in the number of newspapers, and secondly, a sharp increase in the number of newspapers, and the fact that the state informed the people of both domestic and foreign news³.

The socio-political lexicon of that time included communist, communist party, union, trade union, socialism, committee, Bolshevik, kolkhoz, sovkhoz, Komsomol, heavy industry, union, capitalist, centrist, revolution, etc. concepts can be introduced. For example, "the Central Committee of the Communist (Bolshevik) Patriarchate of Uzbekistan, the Tashkent Sahar Committee, the Central Executive Committee of the Soviets, and the Central Soviet of Trade Unions... In this example, a communist (communism) is a member of the Communist Party based on the principles of communism, the Bolshevik Social Democratic Workers' Party, the committee is used in the sense of a state body established to conduct special events or lead a certain field. International and political news: "The worst acts of German-Italian fascism in Spain are the sinking of our "Komsamol" steamer and the attack on our other steamers - a call to war..."; "Relations between the USSR and Japan began to break down in 1936, when the borders were often torn apart, and especially after the signing of a small aid agreement between the USSR and Mongolia," etc. "Mr. Kingsbury Smith, the general director of the American "International News Service" agency in Europe, addressed Mr. G. M. Malenkov on the occasion of the New Year and asked him to answer some questions."

According to the function of the Soviet era publicist, the attractiveness and impact of press texts depended on the attitude of promotion and evaluation. Words of this type, such as goldsmith, goldsmith, field queen, steel horse, steel horse statues, steel skirt, airliner, silver fiber, white gold, etc., were used to increase the impression. "At the meeting of the Supreme Council of the USSR on January 14, the Minister of Internal Affairs of the USSR V. Pugo said: On January 12, peace reigned in the republic. However, Lithuanian radio and television intensified the situation and intensified the anti-Soviet propaganda... Healthy forces, people's comrades tried to stop the slanderous company in front of the radio and television building. However, the guards met them with sticks and binoculars. When the National Rescue Committee appealed for help to the Soviet army garrison in Vilnius, it sent a military unit consisting of tanks and armored vehicles..."

³ Maxmudov N. Tilimizinng tilla sandig'i. –Toshkent.: G'afur G'ulom nomidagi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi. 2012. – B.12.

In the journalistic style of that time, the terms related to science and technology were chisel, seeder, cultivation, technique, molecule, economy, system, and analysis terms such as synthesis, discovery, biochemistry, and space. We can observe that our country has achieved great achievements in the socio-political sphere in its lexicon. If we can see the differences between the years in the journalistic style, we can see the participation of the following lexemes: peace, freedom, democracy, solidarity, ultimatum, appeal, and terms such as rally, security, and peace conference were used. offices performed extensive activities. More than 100 draft laws, more than 1,500 by-laws were issued with legal opinions" and others. Yo. Odilov showed that the development of the Uzbek journalistic language in the period of globalization is manifested in the following: lexical, semantic, and grammatical development.

A) Lexical development:

1. The emergence of new creations.
2. The emergence of new lexical forms.
3. Reactivation of obsolete words.
4. Formation of new generation abbreviations.
5. Acquisition of new words.

B) Semantic development:

1. The emergence of new meanings in words.
2. Expansion of word meanings.
3. Use of words in figurative senses.

C) Grammatical development:

1. Activation of the use of certain morphological forms.
2. Emergence and activation of new syntactic structures.
3. The formation of certain sentence patterns.

In fact, after independence, word changes and linguistic processes in the Uzbek language began to be reflected in journalistic texts. This is because this method serves as the main mediator in illuminating the political and social situation of society. Of course, society's political, social, economic, diplomatic, etc. changes that took place in the fields are reflected in the language, which is reflected in the language⁴.

The newspaper began to organize journalistic texts in the socio-political lexicon from units related to various fields (political, diplomatic, economic, national economy, cultural, social, etc.), that is, from new words and phrases: the Republic of Uzbekistan, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, commitment, holiday spirit, labor honors, trade union, Central Committee, Cabinet, community, etc. Due to a series of changes, reforms, and innovations in the state administration with the honor of independence, term systems, and language units were reshaped in some sense, and the process of naming them became more complicated⁵. As a result, since it was impossible to express broad concepts within the framework of concepts that had become archaism, several changes took place in the language lexicon and their use became active: independence, freedom, religious tolerance, governor, minister, council, district, region, Oliy Majlis, reform, community, tolerance. "The important and urgent tasks

⁴ Mirtojiev M., Mahmudov N. Til va Madaniyat. – T.: O'zbekiston, 1992. – S.8.

⁵ Najimov A.Sh. Mustaqillik yillarida qoraqalpoq tili ijtimoiy -siyosiy leksikaning rivojlanishi. Filol.bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dis.avtoreferati.. –Nukus. 2021. – B.14.

defined in the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, at the meeting dedicated to youth issues, are the responsibility and at the same time very good work to educate the new generation, which is the foundation of our future, to bring it to adulthood intellectually and physically... the great future of our country, our tomorrow, our free and prosperous life, and what place Uzbekistan will occupy in the world community in the 21st century - all of this depends, first of all, on what kind of people the new generation, our growing children will be" etc. At the same time, the changes taking place in society, the journalistic lexicon of the newspaper, in terms of reflecting various fields, as well as socio-political words, terms related to all forms of science and technology, words specific to official style, various professional terms, as well as words specific to artistic style are also unique. began to be used in style. At the same time, the use of elements of speech and artistic style has acquired its character. In the 50th issue of 2019 of "Adolat" newspaper, "Is the city big for shame?" In the article under the title "Or Farangs, the masters of the non-existent", the freedom of speech in the coverage of the political and social topic was demonstrated in the journalistic text⁶.

We quote an excerpt from the article and pay attention to the presence of a socio-political lexicon in the text: Uzbekistan is on the verge of a major political process - the elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, regional, city, and district Councils of People's Deputies. Elections are of great importance in the implementation of the program tasks of the democratic reforms implemented in the country, and strategic development for the near and far future. Also, pre-election propaganda events are being organized in the regions of our country, and propaganda events and rallies are being organized to reveal the goals and tasks of the parties... So, the "XXI Asr" newspaper confirmed that ambulances participated in the rally held almost two months ago. and published a critical article in the issue of December 12. As we can see, the lack of a lexical aspect in modern journalism in this respect has expanded the task possibility, ensuring the originality of journalism. The diachronic study of the socio-political lexicon showed that the changes in the structure of the social and political lexicon of the Uzbek language have undergone many changes.

The presence of inconsistencies between the term and the lexicon in the socio-political lexicon indicates the current state of the socio-political lexicon in the language. The socio-political lexicon has a long history of development. The earliest words related to statehood are found in the ancient book "Avesta". With its historical formation, this social institution of society has developed over centuries. This process, of course, is reflected in the language, especially in its historical lexicon. Therefore, it is natural for the socio-political lexicon to emerge from words related to different languages.

Conclusion. Thus, the historical study of the development of the socio-political lexicon in the journalistic style based on primary sources, the emergence and formation of the press, and determining the features of the journalistic style of the newspaper are considered important tasks in world linguistics. After all, the role and place of information exchange in human activity are very big. Social and political information is mainly used in the management of society. Accordingly, the lexicon of this field will be activated within the

⁶ Ne'matov H., Rasulov R. O'zbek tili sistem leksikolog'iyasi asoslari. –Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1995. –B.7.

framework of its topic or the problem is covered. Social media requires the use of the lexicon of various fields in the coverage of relevant and relevant issues to the audience. Political information also has the same characteristics as social information.

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